

Publication Guide in the Romanian Journal of Military Social Work (RJMSW)

Editorial Standards and Publication Ethics

Publishing in the Romanian Journal of Military Social Work (RJMSW) represents an opportunity for students, defence sector specialists, researchers, practitioners and members of the academic and professional community to make their contributions known in an essential niche field.

We aim to maintain the highest standards of scientific rigour, which is why the manuscript selection process will be thorough and transparent. All works submitted for evaluation must be original, unpublished and must add value to knowledge in the field of military social work or related disciplines — psychology, sociology and resilience — offering valuable perspectives on the psychosocial well-being of military personnel, veterans and their families.

Pillars of the editorial process

Diversity and inclusion

We encourage contributions from a wide range of authors, including students, master's and doctoral candidates, university researchers and academics, active and reserve military personnel, veterans, social workers, psychologists, physicians, legal experts, journalists specialising in military and social affairs, representatives of veterans' organisations and NGOs, as well as specialists from military institutions, governmental bodies and international organisations such as NATO and the EU.

Academic integrity

Rigorous verification of originality through anti-plagiarism systems and tools for detecting content generated by Generative Artificial Intelligence (Generative AI), in order to respect copyright and academic standards.

The peer-review system

Each manuscript will undergo a double-blind editorial review process, guaranteeing the objectivity of the evaluation regardless of the author's rank or affiliation.

Practical impact

We focus on studies that can be applied to improving the quality of life and psychosocial well-being of veterans, personnel on mission and their families.

Alignment with international standards

We encourage authors to use APA 7 citation norms (American Psychological Association, 7th edition) to facilitate the indexing of research in international databases.

Ethical responsibility

By submitting a manuscript to RJMSW, authors assume responsibility for the accuracy of the data and compliance with ethical standards in research involving human subjects, where applicable.

1. Format and Language

- Manuscripts must be submitted in **.doc / .docx** format, in **English or Romanian**.
- Proper grammar and clarity are required.

2. Article Structure

- **Length:** 4–8 pages.
- **Formatting:** Times New Roman, 12 pt, 1.5 line spacing.
- **Abstract & Keywords:** Required in the language of the manuscript.
- **Citations:** APA 7th Edition style.
- **Ethics & Integrity:** Plagiarism and the use of Generative AI are strictly prohibited.

Mandatory Statements

Authors are required to include the following statements at the end of the manuscript:

Conflict of Interest: "The author declares no conflict of interest."

Funding: "This research received no specific grant."

Submission

Email: redactie@rrasm.ro

Online form: <https://rrasm.ro/formular-expediere-articol/>

